

Synthesis, spectral, thermal and antibacterial studies of copper(II) complexes of a Schiff base derived from 2,3-dimethyl-1-phenyl-4-aminopyrazol-5-one

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Abstract : The Schiff base 2,3-dimethyl-1-phenyl-4-(2,5-dihydroxyacetophenone)-5-pyrazolone (DHAAP) was prepared by reacting 4-aminoantipyrine with 2,5-dihydroxy acetophenone and a series of metal complexes with this ligand were synthesized by reaction with copper(II) having the compositions $[\text{Cu}(\text{DHAAP})_2(\text{Cl})_2]$, $[\text{Cu}(\text{DHAAP})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$, $[\text{Cu}(\text{DHAAP})_2(\text{ClO}_4)_2]$, $[\text{Cu}(\text{DHAAP})_2(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2]$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{DHAAP})_2(\text{NCS})(\text{Cl})]$ (where DHAAP = dihydroxyacetophenoneazoantipyrine). The complexes were characterized on the basis of elemental analyses, molar conductance, magnetic susceptibility data, UV-Visible, IR and ESR spectral studies. The thermal behaviour of the complex, $[\text{Cu}(\text{DHAAP})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$ was investigated by thermogravimetric technique. X-Ray diffraction studies of the complex, $[\text{Cu}(\text{DHAAP})_2(\text{Cl})_2]$ indicated orthorhombic crystal lattice with $a = 13.6118 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 5.2759 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 3.2758 \text{ \AA}$. The ligand exhibits a neutral bidentate behaviour in all the complexes, coordinating to the metal ion through carbonyl oxygen and azomethine nitrogen. The X-band ESR spectrum of the complex, $[\text{Cu}(\text{DHAAP})_2(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2]$ shows an axial ligand field symmetry. The ligand and the complex $[\text{Cu}(\text{DHAAP})_2(\text{NCS})(\text{Cl})]$ were screened for their antibacterial activities against gram positive and gram negative bacteria.

Keywords : Copper(II), Schiff base, thermogravimetry.

Introduction

Copper is one of the transition metals which has given abundant number of coordination compounds. The dipositive state is the most important oxidation state for copper though the other two states namely +1 and +3 are also known¹. The Cu^{2+} has a d^9 configuration, which makes it subject to Jahn-Teller distortion when placed in an octahedral or tetrahedral environment². The stereochemistry is affected by the extend of Jahn-Teller distortion. A number of copper proteins including enzymes have been isolated and the copper sites are found to be active centres for many enzymes^{3,4}.

Studies on Schiff base complexes of Cu^{II} are of great interest. Copper(II) ion has been reported to form stable complexes with tridentate Schiff bases, salicyldimino alkylpyridines etc. Biologically active Schiff bases derived from 5-methyl-2-hydroxy acetophenone and glycine have been reported to show chelating behaviour towards copper(II) ions to give neutral complexes with square planar, tetrahedral and square pyramidal geometries respectively⁵.

Agarwal *et al.*⁶ have synthesized and characterized a novel series of Schiff base copper(II) complexes by con-

densation of 4-aminoantipyrine and various aromatic aldehydes. Tudor Rosu *et al.*⁷ have synthesized copper(II) complexes derived from Schiff base ligands obtained by the condensation of 2-hydroxy benzaldehyde or terephthalic aldehyde with 4-aminoantipyrine. Selvakumar *et al.*⁷ have synthesized copper(II) complexes $[\text{Cu}(\text{L}_1)_2]$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{L}_2)_2]$, where L_1 and L_2 are the Schiff base ligands derived from 4-aminoantipyrine and substituted salicylaldehydes. Schiff base complexes of oxomolybdenum(V), dioxomolybdenum(VI) and dioxouranium(VI) derived from 4-aminoantipyrine have also been reported⁸.

Owing to the importance of copper(II) complexes, we have isolated and characterized a few new complexes of a potential multidentate Schiff base ligand, 2,3-dimethyl-1-phenyl-4-(2,5-dihydroxyacetophenone)pyrazol-5-one (DHAAP).

Fig. 1. DHAAP

Results and discussion

All the complexes are deeply coloured non-hygroscopic, stable crystalline solids. They are soluble in nitrobenzene and acetonitrile, sparingly soluble in other common organic solvents and insoluble in ether. The molar conductance data (Table 1) show that all the complexes are non-electrolytes⁹. The magnetic moments (Table 1) of copper(II) complexes are in the range 1.88–1.92 B.M., which show normal magnetic behaviour expected for the presence of one unpaired electron of a d^9 configuration. This indicates the absence of any metal-metal interaction in complexes.

vibrational stretching of azomethine $\nu_{C=N}$ group.

The IR spectra of the complexes showed absorption $\sim 3400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating the non participation of -OH group in coordination to the metal ion. The $\nu_{C=O}$ and $\nu_{C=N}$ observed at 1635 and 1585 cm^{-1} respectively in the ligand spectrum are shifted to ~ 1586 and $\sim 1550\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of the complexes suggesting the participation of these groups in coordination¹¹. Thus the ligand exhibits a neutral bidentate behaviour in all the complexes. Also the IR spectra of the complexes shows bands at ~ 506 and $\sim 454\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which may be attributed to ν_{Cu-N} and ν_{Cu-O} respectively.

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of the copper(II) complexes of DHAAP

Complex (Colour)	Analytical data (%) :						Molar conductance			μ_{eff} (B.M.)
	Found (Calcd.)						$(\Omega^{-1}\text{ cm}^2\text{ mol}^{-1})$			
	Cu	C	H	N	S	Cl	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NO}_2$	CH_3CN	CH_3OH	
[Cu(DHAAP) ₂ (Cl) ₂] (Dark brown)	7.64 (7.86)	56.37 (56.40)	4.68 (4.70)	-	-	8.54 (8.77)	2.7	6.8	3.6	1.90
[Cu(DHAAP) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂] (Brown)	7.33 (7.37)	52.56 (52.93)	4.32 (4.41)	12.88 (13.00)	-	-	3.9	9.9	4.2	1.89
[Cu(DHAAP) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₂] (Reddish brown)	7.33 (7.42)	55.80 (56.10)	4.28 (4.44)	-	-	-	15.2	17.2	16.5	1.88
[Cu(DHAAP) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂] (Brownish red)	6.39 (6.78)	48.50 (48.69)	3.83 (4.05)	-	-	7.28 (7.57)	11.6	16.3	15.2	1.92
[Cu(DHAAP) ₂ (NCS)(Cl)] (Brown)	7.60 (7.64)	56.24 (56.31)	4.52 (4.57)	11.64 (11.79)	-	4.15 (4.26)	10.8	16.1	12.3	1.91

Table 2 lists selected vibrational bands and assignment of ligand and their copper(II) complexes. The infrared spectrum of the free ligand exhibited a broad medium intensity band around 3058 cm^{-1} due to intramolecular hydrogen bonded OH group¹⁰. A very sharp band around 1635 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of the ligand is attributed to $\nu_{C=O}$ of pyrazolone ring. Another band observed at 1585 cm^{-1} in the ligand spectrum may be attributed to the

For the perchlorate complex, ν_2 , ν_3 and ν_4 appear as strong and medium intensity bands at 917, 618 and 1142 cm^{-1} respectively indicating a monodentately coordinated perchlorate group¹².

Acetate complex exhibit a strong band $\sim 1487\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and medium intensity band $\sim 1314\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which can be attributed to $\nu_{C=O}$ and ν_{C-O} respectively of acetate group. The position of these vibrations and the magnitude of

Table 2. Spectral data of the ligand DHAAP and its copper(II) complexes

Ligand/ Complexes	Infrared spectra (cm^{-1})					
	ν_{OH} (hydrogen bonded) 3058m	ν_{OH} (free)	$\nu_{C=O}$	$\nu_{C=N}$	ν_{Cu-N}	ν_{Cu-O}
DHAAP	-	-	1635s	1585s	-	-
[Cu(DHAAP) ₂ (Cl) ₂]	-	3429m	1603m	1563m	499w	439w
[Cu(DHAAP) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]	-	3416m	1565s	1560s	506w	454w
[Cu(DHAAP) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₂]	-	3416m	1586s	1553m	498w	426w
[Cu(DHAAP) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂]	-	3416m	1594s	1560s	500w	419w
[Cu(DHAAP) ₂ (NCS)(Cl)]	-	3250m	1619s	1565s	499w	439w

their separation by 173 cm^{-1} supports the coordinated nature of acetate group in a unidentate fashion. The conductance data (Table 1) are also in good agreement with the coordinated nature of acetate group in the complex¹³.

In the IR spectra of the thiocyanate complex, the *N*-coordinated nature is indicated by the $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ ($\sim 2077\text{ cm}^{-1}$), $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ ($\sim 784\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and δNCS ($\sim 472\text{ cm}^{-1}$). The bands $\sim 1487\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (ν_4) and $\sim 1367\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (ν_1) with a separation of about 120 cm^{-1} are suggestive of monodentately coordinated nitrate group¹⁴.

The electronic spectral bands of copper(II) complexes in solution together with the tentative assignments are discussed. All the complexes shows absorption bands at 280, 380 and 690 nm. The former absorption band at 280 nm can be attributed to the $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition, whereas the absorption band at 380 nm may be due to charge transfer transition. The absorption band at 690 nm is attributed to *d-d* transition (${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$). The possibility of distorted octahedral geometry for all the complexes is confirmed by the occurrence of a weak band around 690 nm corresponding to the ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ transition. The

electronic spectral data are in conformity with the magnetic moment values.

The ${}^1\text{H}$ NMR spectrum of the ligand, DHAAP displays two sharp singlets which correspond to the methyl protons. The signals due to $>\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$ protons and $>\text{N}-\text{CH}_3$ protons are observed at δ 2.16 ppm and δ 3.14 ppm respectively. The aromatic protons give sharp multiplets in the region δ 7.30–7.47 ppm. The ligand shows a peak at δ 14.05 ppm characteristic of intramolecular hydrogen bonded OH proton¹⁵. The IR spectral data are also in conformity with these observations.

The complex $[\text{Cu}(\text{DHAAP})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$ undergoes a two stage thermal decomposition as indicated by the DTG peaks at 377 and 570 °C (Fig. 2). The first stage of decomposition is from 357 to 406 °C in the TG curve which corresponds to the elimination of the coordinated species DHAAP and NO_3 and in the second stage (547–667 °C) the complete decomposition of the complex to CuO takes place. The final mass loss observed agrees with the values calculated for the conversion of the complex to its metal oxide (CuO).

Fig. 2. TG and DTG curves of $[\text{Cu}(\text{DHAAP})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$.

The order parameters for the first and second stages of decomposition are two. The energy of activation for the first stage of decomposition is 170.118 kJ mol⁻¹ and that of second stage of decomposition is 478.521 kJ mol⁻¹ respectively¹⁶. The ΔS values for the two stages of decomposition are -90.360 and 208.283 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹ respectively. The kinetic parameters are calculated using Coats-Redfern equation and the computational details for the two stages of thermal decomposition of the complex are given in Table 3.

X-Ray powder diffractions of the complex [Cu(DHAAP)₂(Cl)₂] were also examined (Fig. 3). The main peaks have been indexed and the d_{hkl} values compared with the calculated ones using Hesse and Lipson's procedure¹⁷ (Table 4). The observed values fit well with orthorhombic system. The lattice constants for the complex [Cu(DHAAP)₂(Cl)₂] were found to be $A = 0.0032$, $B = 0.0213$ and $C = 0.0552$ and unit cell dimensions $a = 13.6118 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 5.2759 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 3.2758 \text{ \AA}$.

The ESR spectrum of the complex, [Cu(DHAAP)₂(CH₃COO)₂] was recorded in polycrystalline form at room temperature. The ESR parameters were found to be $g_{\parallel} = 2.07$, $g_{\perp R} = 2.00$ and $g_{av} = 2.02$ respectively. The trends $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp R} > g_e$ (free ion value = 2.0036) observed

Table 3. Kinetic parameters for the two stages of thermal decomposition of [Cu(DHAAP)₂(NO₃)₂]

Stage	Peak temp. (K)	Activation energy, E (kJ mol ⁻¹)	Pre-exponential factor, A (s ⁻¹)	Entropy of activation, ΔS (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)
I	650	170.118	2.584×10^8	-90.360
II	843	478.521	1.326×10^{24}	208.283

Fig. 3. X-Ray diffraction pattern of [Cu(DHAAP)₂(Cl)₂].

for this complex shows that the unpaired electron is localized in $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital of Cu^{II} ion and the spectrum is characteristic of axial symmetry¹⁸.

Table 4. X-Ray diffraction data of $[\text{Cu}(\text{DHAAP})_2(\text{Cl})_2]$

Line	<i>h k l</i>	$\sin^2 \theta$ (Obsd.)	$\sin^2 \theta$ (Calcd.)	Relative intensity (%)
1	1 0 0	0.0315	0.0327	18.89
2	2 1 0	0.0335	0.0350	100.00
3	1 4 1	0.0435	0.0447	29.23
4	4 0 0	0.0515	0.0519	82.03
5	0 0 1	0.0560	0.0566	35.20
6	1 0 1	0.0589	0.0598	6.45
7	2 0 1	0.0680	0.0684	5.67
8	0 1 1	0.0765	0.0779	8.65
9	1 2 0	0.0932	0.0936	5.20
10	2 2 0	0.1012	0.1017	7.80
11	3 2 0	0.1095	0.1098	8.88
12	4 1 1	0.1201	0.1205	4.26
13	0 2 1	0.1415	0.1416	4.02
14	1 3 0	0.1972	0.1977	4.20
15	0 1 2	0.2370	0.2373	4.23

control. The test bacteria were inoculated onto Mueller Hinton Agar (MHA) to give a lawn culture. The test and control sample discs were placed on the media and incubated at 35 to 37 °C for 18 to 24 h. The bacterial screening data of the ligand and its complex are given in Table 5. From the result, it is clear that both the ligand and the complex do not show any antibacterial activity. In other words, the two bacteria are tolerant to DHAAP and its copper(II) thiocyanate complex at the concentrations studied.

On the basis of the above physicochemical studies, a distorted octahedral geometry is tentatively suggested for the complexes.

Experimental

4-Aminoantipyrine (E. Merck, Germany), 2,5-dihydroxyacetophenone (Sisco Research Laboratory, Mumbai), copper(II) acetate (B.D.H., England) were used as such. All other chemicals used were of A.R. grade.

Metal, chloride, perchlorate and sulphur in the com-

Table 5. Test results of antibacterial activity of the ligand DHAAP and its complex $[\text{Cu}(\text{DHAAP})_2(\text{NCS})(\text{Cl})]$

Test sample	Concentration per disc	Zone of inhibition	
		<i>E. coli</i> ATCC 25922	<i>S. aureus</i> ATCC 25923
DHAAP	10 µg	Nil	Nil
	20 µg	Nil	Nil
	40 µg	Nil	Nil
	80 µg	Nil	Nil
	100 µg	Nil	Nil
$[\text{Cu}(\text{DHAAP})_2(\text{NCS})(\text{Cl})]$	10 µg	Nil	Nil
	20 µg	Nil	Nil
	40 µg	Nil	Nil
	80 µg	Nil	Nil
	100 µg	Nil	Nil
	Gentamicin - 10 mcg	18 mm	24 mm
Negative control	Nil	Nil	

The ligand DHAAP and the complex, $[\text{Cu}(\text{DHAAP})_2(\text{NCS})(\text{Cl})]$ have been screened for their possible antibacterial activity by Disc Diffusion method¹⁹ (Kirby Bauer method) against gram positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 25923 and the gram negative bacteria *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922 at different concentrations using gentamicin as positive control and sterile filter paper aseptically impregnated with methanol as negative

plexes were estimated by standard methods²⁰. Elemental analyses were carried out at Sophisticated Test and Instrumentation Centre, Kochi. The IR spectra of the ligand and the complexes were recorded in the region 4000–400 cm^{-1} on a Perkin-Elmer 397 spectrophotometer. The electronic spectra of the complexes in methanol were recorded on JASCO V-550 UV-Visible spectrophotometer (Japan) in the range 900–200 nm. The conductance value of the

Fig. 4. Suggested structures for the copper(II) complexes of DHAAP.

complexes in nitrobenzene, acetonitrile and methanol (*ca.* 10⁻³ M) were measured using digital control dynamics conductivity meter. ¹H NMR spectrum of the ligand was recorded in CDCl₃ on a 300 MHz Bruker Advance-300 NMR spectrometer using TMS as reference material. The ESR spectrum of the complex was run on a Varian E-112 X-Q band spectrometer with DPPH as reference material. X-Ray powder diffraction pattern of the complex was recorded using Philips X-ray PW 1710 diffractometer. The magnetic susceptibilities at room temperature were measured on a Guoy balance using Hg[Co(NCS)₄] as calibrant. Diamagnetic corrections for various atoms and structural units were computed using Pascal's constants. The thermal decomposition study was made using a Mettler TG-50 thermobalance in oxygen atmosphere at a heating

rate of 10 °C/min. Antibacterial nature of the ligand and the complex was tested by disc diffusion method.

Synthesis of ligand :

The Schiff base was prepared by mixing equimolar solutions of 2,5-dihydroxyacetophenone with 4-aminoantipyrine in methanol and refluxing the reaction mixture on a water bath for about 1–2 h. On cooling, bright-yellow crystals of DHAAP were obtained. They were filtered, washed with methanol and recrystallised from hot methanol and dried over P₄O₁₀ *in vacuo*. The purity was tested by m.p. determination, IR spectra and was also characterized by NMR spectral data.

Synthesis of Cu^{II} complexes :

The complexes having the general formula [Cu(L)₂(X)₂] (where L = DHAAP and X = Cl, NO₃, CH₃COO, ClO₄) were prepared by the addition of methanolic solution of the metal salt (2.5 mmol) to a hot methanolic solution of the ligand, DHAAP (2.5 mmol) with stirring and was refluxed on a water bath for ~2 h. The solid complex separated on concentrating the solution, was suction filtered, washed with methanol and dried over P₄O₁₀ *in vacuo*.

The thiocyanate complex, [Cu(DHAAP)₂(NCS)(Cl)] was prepared by adding ~0.5 g of ammonium thiocyanate to the methanolic solution of Cu^{II} chloride (2 mmol) stirred well, filtered and the clear solution was refluxed for ~2 h with hot methanolic solution of the ligand. The solid complex obtained on volume reduction was filtered, washed with methanol and dried over P₄O₁₀ *in vacuo*.

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References

1. E. G. West, "Copper and it's alloys", Ellis West/Ellis Horwood Ltd., New York, 1982.
2. H. A. Jahn and E. Teller, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1937, **166**, 220; 1938, **164**, 117; M. L. Harikumaran Nair and L. Shamlal, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2009, **86**, 133.

- M. G. Clark and R. C. Burns, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 1034.
- D. W. Smith, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, **5**, 2236.
- L. J. Taylor and W. M. Coleman, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1981, **63**, 183.
- V. Yogesh Kumar, N. R. S. Mayur and B. S. C. Sumitra, *J. Serb. Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **69**, 991; N. Raman, C. Thangaraja and S. Johnsonraja, *Cent. Euro. J. Chem.*, 2005, **3**, 537; R. K. Agarwal, L. Singh and D. K. Sharma, *Bioin. Chem. Appl.*, 2006, article ID 59509.
- T. Rosu, S. Pasculescu, V. Lazar, C. Chifriuc and R. Cernat, *Molecules*, 2006, **11**, 904; S. P. Mosae, E. Suresh and P. S. Subramanian, *Polyhedron*, 2007, **26**, 749.
- A. Sheela, M. S. Pramila Gladis and M. L. Harikumar Nair, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **84**, 329; M. L. Harikumar Nair, M. S. Pramila Gladis and A. Sheela, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **84**, 861.
- D. N. Sathyanarayanan and C. C. Patel, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1967, **5**, 360; M. L. Harikumar Nair and C. P. Prabhakaran, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1998, **37**, 453.
- William Kemp, "Organic Spectroscopy", The Macmillan Press, New York, 1975.
- M. L. Harikumar Nair and A. T. Mariamma, *Asian J. Chem.*, 2006, **16**, 285.
- Sali Thomas and M. L. Harikumar Nair, *Asian J. Chem.*, 2005, **17**, 2657; D. K. Koppikar, P. V. Sivapulliah, L. Ramakrishnan and S. Soundararajan, *Struct. Bonding*, 1978, **34**, 135.
- M. L. Harikumar Nair and G. Mathew, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **82**, 886.
- V. K. Rema Devi. A. Fernandez and M. Alaudeen, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **83**, 537.
- William Kemp, "NMR in Chemistry, A Multinuclear Introduction", Mc. Millan Publishing Company, 1986; D. H. Williams and I. Fleming. "Spectroscopic Methods in Organic Chemistry", 4th ed., Tata McGraw Hill, New Delhi, 1988.
- A. W. Coats and J. P. Redfern, *Nature*, 1964, **201**, 68.
- R. Hesse, *Acta Crystallogr.*, 1948, **1**, 200. H. Lipson, *Acta Crystallogr.*, 1949, **2**, 43; N. F. M. Henry, H. Lipson and W. A. Wooster, "The Interpretation of X-Ray Diffraction Photographs", Mc. Millan, London, 1951.
- W. Gordey, "Theory and Applications of Electron Spin Resonance", John Wiley. New York, 1980.
- R. Ananthanarayan and J. C. Panikar, "Text Book of Microbiology", Orient Longman, 1999.
- A. I. Vogel, "A Text Book of Quantitative Chemical Analysis", 5th ed., ELBS with Longman, 1996; M. Saukir, S. P. Varkey and P. S. Hammed, *J. Chem. Res.*, 1993, **11**, 2964.